

2. T. N. GHOSH and A. R. CHAUDHARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 268.
3. H. P. KAUTMANN and P. SCHULTZ, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, **22**, 273.
4. J. S. SHUKLA, H. H. SINGH and S. S. PARMAR, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1969, **311**, 187.
5. B. R. BAKER and WALLANCE T. ASHTOU, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, **16**, 209.
6. E. RICHARD, MOOR and ARTHUR FURST, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1504.
7. C. GEORGE, N. MATRIN and R. ROY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, **16**, 1402.
8. D. R. VERMA, K. N. SAREEN and M. L. GUJRAL, *Indian J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 1959, **3**, 168.
9. S. IRWIN, cited in "Evaluation of drug activities Pharmacometrics" (Eds. D. R. Laurence and A. L. Bacharach) by J. R. VANE, 1964, **1**, 33 (Academic Press, London).
10. S. S. PARMAR, C. DWIVEDI, A. CHAUDHARI and T. K. GUPTA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 99.
11. C. W. TOBER, H. TOBER, and S. ROSENFHAL in "Method Enzymology", Vol. II, p. 390.

On the Dicumyl Peroxide Vulcanisation of Rubber

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Manuscript received 7 May 1977, revised 14 April 1978,
accepted 9 July 1980

DICUMYL peroxide (DCP) vulcanisation of rubbers has attracted wide interest in recent years because of its simple chemistry and quantitative results where one carbon to carbon crosslink is formed per molecule of peroxide decomposed¹. The sulfur vulcanisation of natural rubber (NR) is known to be characterised by a reversion in crosslinking, just after reaching the optimum cure time, and it also produces vulcanisate with poor aging properties.

The addition of DCP in sulfur curing system checks both these defects through the inclusion of Carbon-Carbon crosslinks. However, the accelerators, present in the system, may affect adversely² on the DCP-NR curing system. In the present paper, the nature and the extent of the effect of the commonly used accelerators on the DCP-NR vulcanisation system has been investigated. The accelerators used are 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT), diphenyl guanidine (DPG) and tetramethyl thiuram disulfide (TMTD).

Experimental

The following sets of compounding formulations were studied. All the formulations given below are in Phr (Parts per hundred of rubber).

NR 100	NR 100	NR 100
DCP 1.0	DCP 1.0	DCP 1.0
MBT, DPG	MBT 1.0	MBT 1.0
or TMTD 0.0,	DPG 0.0, 0.5,	TMTD 0.0, 0.5,
0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0	1.0	1.0

Mixing was done on a laboratory size two roll mill at 50° to a constant Mooney viscosity. Each stock was cured in an electrically heated press at 140° ± 1° and a pressure of 281 psi for various times. Crosslink density of each vulcanisate was determined by equilibrium swelling in benzene as described in the earlier publication³ of this laboratory.

Results and Discussion

Vulcanisation of natural rubber by dicumyl peroxide has been studied by several workers and the crosslinking reaction has been established beyond doubt to follow a free radical mechanism which can be summarised as follows :

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So the effect on crosslink density due to the presence of additives would mean the interaction of the peroxide radicals with those additives.

Effect of Individual Accelerators on DCP Vulcanisation :

Of the three individual accelerators studied, the course of crosslinking by DCP in pre-ence of one representative, namely TMTD, has been shown in Fig. 1. However, the effect of these accelerators on the initial rate of vulcanisation and maximum crosslink density (corresponding to cure time of 150 mins.) of DCP vulcanisation has been summarised in Fig. 2. The salient points observed from these results are as follows :

(i) Each of these accelerators, MBT, DPG and TMTD, inhibits DCP vulcanisation depending on

Fig. 1. Variation of crosslink density (I/M'_c) in systems containing DCP and TMTD (variable) as a function of cure time.

Fig. 2. Change in maximum crosslink density (I/M'_c)_{max} and initial rate of crosslinking on the variable accelerators' concentration.

the amount of the accelerator present in the system (Fig. 1).

(ii) The difference in behaviour of these accelerators towards DCP vulcanisation are only in the degree of inhibition at different stages of vulcanisation. Thus, MBT reduces the initial crosslink density more effectively than the others (Fig. 2) whereas the reduction in maximum crosslink density is most with TMTD. And the action of DPG is mild in both the respects (Fig. 2).

All these observations can be explained by reaction schemes where DCP free radicals, responsible for crosslinking, are captured either by accelerator molecules or its decomposition products.

